

PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS AND CLINICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF CHRONIC PANCREATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH HYPOTHYROIDISM**Ratsa V.,***Assistant, Internal Medicine Department, Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi, 58002***Moskaliuk M.,***4th-year student of the 26th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Melnychenko O.,***4th-year student of the 26th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine***Zhulavska L.***4th-year student of the 26th group at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878676>**Abstract**

At the present stage, much attention is paid to the peculiarities of the course of comorbid diseases of internal organs. It is due to the fact, that comorbidity or polymorbidity makes it difficult to determine which disease dominates the common clinical symptoms at each stage of exacerbation. During the treatment of patients with a comorbid or polymorbid course, it is very important to prevent polypharmacy, even, taking into account the general mechanisms of development, the possibility of common use of a number of drugs poses some difficulties in planning and carrying out rehabilitation measures. [1] Correct treatment tactic is possible only after a detailed study of the etiological and pathogenetic features of these diseases, taking into account in detail the mechanisms of development and interaction of these diseases on the quality and life expectancy of such patients. [2] Despite the large number of studies in pancreatology and endocrinology, the problems of prevention, diagnosis, medical correction and rehabilitation of patients with chronic pancreatitis (CP) and hypothyroidism still remain relevant, because the increase in the number of patients who suffering from these pathologies is gaining the scale of a global problem. [3, 4]

Keywords: chronic pancreatitis (CP), hypothyroidism, comorbidity.

Presenting main material. CP is a progressive fibro-inflammatory disease characterized by recurrent painful attacks of pancreatitis and the successive latent development of chronic, debilitating pain over the next 3-5 years after the initial episode. [5,6]

In the structure of diseases of the digestive system, CP ranks 3rd among all pathologies of the gastrointestinal tract and is from 5% to 9% per 100,000 population, i.e. approximately 4.0-10.0 cases per 100,000 population for a year. The prevalence of disease is from 26.7 to 50.0 cases per 100,000 population. In the last 30 years, the incidence of CP in Ukraine has more than doubled and amounts to approximately 1 million patients; these indicators are 4 times higher than in Europe. Nowadays, according to the Institute of Gastroenterology of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine, about 1 million patients suffer from CP. More than 20 years of suffering from CP increases the risk of developing pancreas cancer by 5 times. Within 10 years, as a result, about 30% eventually die, and in 20 years - more than half of patients with CP, which makes the problem of CP one of the main problems of internal medicine and, in particular, of clinical gastroenterology. [7,8]

Studying in detail the statistical data on the distribution and hospitalization of CP and hypothyroidism treatment facilities in Ukraine as of 2018, (analyzing the data of the Statistics Center of the MOH of Ukraine) , 185 484 hospitalized patients with diseases of the endocrine system, nutritional and metabolic disorders were recorded, of which 3,236 were hypothyroidism patients .If we analyze the spread of the disease in the Chernivtsi Region, then 6,293 hospitalized patients

with diseases of the endocrine system, nutritional and metabolic disorders were recorded, including 86 patients with hypothyroidism. Official data, for 2018 it's 598 382 hospitalized patients with diseases of digestive system, of which 108 449 patients were hospitalized with CP, a similar analysis of the Chernivtsi Region, respectively, 15 723 inpatient cases of patients with diseases of the digestive organs, of which 3 316 were patients with CP.

Hypothyroidism is a common condition in which the thyroid gland (TG) produces an insufficient amount of hormones for the functioning of peripheral tissues, i.e., a condition where the production of thyroid hormones (TH) does not correspond to the body's metabolic needs. [9] It is a well-known fact that TH play an important role in energy metabolism and change the functioning of other endocrine glands; however, their effects on pancreatic function (PG) have not yet been fully investigated. [10]

In the 21st century, world scientists are actively studying the role of vascular endothelium in the occurrence and progression of many diseases. The endothelium, as the largest diffusely dispersed active endocrine organ, is capable of continuous production of biologically active substances (the mass of all endotheliocytes reaches approximately one and a half kilograms), the dysfunction of which is a component of the pathogenesis of almost all vascular diseases. The balance between the formation of vasoconstrictor and vasodilator substances is the key to the normal functioning of the endothelium. [11]. Thyroid hormones affect endothelial dysfunction, as a result of deterioration of the process of vasodilatation in patients with thyroid-stimulating

hormone levels higher than normal. TH contribute to the relaxation of skeletal muscles, affecting the vessels of smooth muscles, that is, they act as vasodilators. Hypothyroidism leads to an increase in vascular resistance and vasoconstriction in systemic and renal vessels.[12] It is also known that the biological effects of thyroid hormones determine the existence of a connection between the level of TH in the body and the processes of free radical oxidation of lipids, lipid peroxidation, protein peroxide modification, the oxidant-antioxidant system with the formation of reactive oxygen species it's processes performed by numerous regulatory functions and are non-specific markers of the pathological state of internal organs.[13] Oxidative stress resulting from the accumulation of high levels of reactive oxygen species [14] activates the stellate cells of the pancreas, which leads to the deposition of collagen extracellular matrix and causes pancreas fibrosis. [15]

Analyzing data from the literature and the results of experimental and clinical investigations, it can be concluded that at the cellular level, an increase in the production of reactive oxygen species is associated with the development of CP. During the metabolism of alcohol, smoking and neutralization of food toxins in the liver, excessive production of reactive oxygen species in the acinar cells of the pancreas significantly increases, this leads to suppression of the antioxidant system and disruption of the functioning of the acinar cells of the pancreas. [16]

Thyroid hormones (TH) play a leading role in metabolic processes in the human body. Disorder of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism in hypothyroidism occurs due to a change in homeostasis in TH-sensitive tissues. The processes of liponeogenesis and lipolysis depend on their activity [17]. Their lipolytic effect is due to the activation of hormone-sensitive lipase and start the lipid hydrolysis process, and, as a result, the reduction of the total amount of fat. When the level of TH is decrease, the rate of synthesis of fatty acids in the liver and subcutaneous adipose tissue and the rate of lipolysis decrease [18]. The cholesterol level is determined by thyroid activity [19]. With hypothyroidism, the rate of cholesterol synthesis and its excretion with bile decreases, this leads to an increase in the content of total cholesterol and low-density lipoproteins in the serum; manifestations of dyslipidemia are proportional to the duration of hypothyroidism [20]. Dyslipidemic changes that occur with hypothyroidism play the role of a precursor in the progression of exocrine insufficiency. [21] Hypothyroidism induces a significant increase in lipid peroxidation and decreases the activity of antioxidant enzymes. These data indicate that oxidative stress, which occurs in hypothyroidism, may play a key role in the progression of exocrine and endocrine dysfunction of pancreas. [22]

When studying the common pathogenesis, it is worth paying attention to the proteolysis system, which normally underlies many vital physiological processes (fibrinolysis, hemocoagulation, complement activation), and plays a key role in maintaining homeostasis. Non-specific proteinases and their inhibitors, as individual components of a complete system, can play the

role of damaging factors, activating the processes of hemocoagulation, which leads to direct damage to the vessels of the microcirculatory channel [23].

During our research, 112 patients were examined : 55 patients with CP, 57 patients with CP and hypothyroidism. The clinical symptoms in patients with CP combined with hypothyroidism were associated with the duration of the comorbid course for more than 6 years with the predominance of complaints of pain in the left hypochondrium in 73.3%, less frequently in both hypochondria in 16.7% and in 6.5 % of patients the pain was localized in the pyloroduodenal region. It should be noted, that the intensity of pain in most patients was moderate, which was the reason for hypodiagnosis of CP in patients with combined pathology. Dyspeptic syndrome manifested itself in 63.3% of patients, appetite disorders in 13.3% of patients, vomiting in 56.7% of patients, heartburn in 23.3% of patients, flatulence in 76.7% of patients, stool disorders in 43.3% of patients. Along with this, the syndromes of gastric and intestinal dyspepsia, in contrast to the pain syndrome, were more bothered, which can be explained by the increase in hyposecretory phenomena that occur in the glands of digestive system with the comorbidity of these diseases. Often, patients noted autonomic vegetative disorders, in particular, sleep disturbances in 72% of patients, blood pressure instability in 46% of patients, adynamia in 60% of patients, menstrual cycle disorders in 27% of patients, high sensitive to cold in 33.3% of patients, memory and attention disorders in 53.3% of patients.Irritability was noted in 71.8% of patients with CP and 68.2% of patients with CP combined with hypothyroidism. Based on the data we obtained, metabolic changes prevailed in patients with a comorbid state of CP combined with hypothyroidism, which, according to the data obtained, worsens the clinical course in both groups and the adaptive capabilities of patients in general.

Conclusions. The increase in the number of cases of combined thyroid dysfunction with gastro-pathology requires an in-depth study of the causes of the occurrence and connection of these processes.The study of proteolytic and fibrinolytic activity, indicators of oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction in the combination of CP with hypothyroidism gives a possibility to clearly determine their role in the pathogenesis of these comorbid pathologies. It is worth paying great attention to genetic risk factors for the development, or on the contrary, protection of the occurrence of CP. Nowadays, less than half of the genetic risk factors for the development of CP have been identified. The same applies to protective factors that can prevent the occurrence of pancreatitis, performing a protective effect. Various gene mutations and polymorphisms determine a person's susceptibility to the development of CP, the severity and progression of the disease. Researching the peculiarities of the mutual influence and course of CP in patients with hypothyroidism, optimization of therapeutic treatment schemes is a very promising area of medicine. It will make it possible to avoid the appearance of complications and the development of disability in the future.

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